

ENHANCING TEACHER PRODUCTIVITY THROUGH SCHOOL SUPPORTS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the extent of instruction-related support provided to teachers in selected schools in Trinidad, Bohol, during the School Year 2022-2023, with the aim of informing a strategic plan to enhance teacher productivity. The research explores various demographic and professional factors among teachers and administrators, including age, gender, educational attainment, years of service, performance, and participation in relevant leadership training and seminars. Additionally, it examines the perceived level of support received by teachers in areas such as administrative assistance, peer collaboration, the learning environment, professional development opportunities, productivity recognition, and rewards. The findings reveal a significant gender imbalance, with female teachers and administrators predominantly outnumbering their male counterparts. Performance evaluations indicate consistent "Very Satisfactory" ratings across the board, although teachers report lower levels of productivity recognition compared to administrators. Both groups perceive the learning environment and professional development opportunities positively, although teachers express only moderate satisfaction with school culture. A key finding is the significant relationship between the extent of instruction-related support and teacher performance, underscoring the importance of targeted support mechanisms in enhancing educational outcomes. Based on these insights, the study recommends actions to address gender diversity, improve equity in productivity recognition, and strengthen institutional support and school culture. These recommendations aim to foster a more inclusive, supportive, and effective educational environment that enhances teacher satisfaction and productivity, ultimately benefiting both educators and students.

Keywords: *Educational Environment, Gender Diversity, Instructional Support, Professional Development, and Teacher Productivity*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are the backbone of any educational system, playing a crucial role in shaping the minds of future generations. Their productivity directly influences student learning outcomes and, by extension, the broader societal future (Constantinou & Wijnen, 2022). Parojenog (2020) emphasizes that teachers are versatile, equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to handle diverse learners. Each day, they rise to the challenge of meeting the unique needs of every student.

However, teacher productivity is not solely a reflection of their abilities and dedication. It is also significantly influenced by the support they receive from the school system (Jourdan et al., 2021). In this context, 'school support' is a multifaceted concept that includes administrative backing, peer collaboration, the quality of the learning environment, parental involvement, and opportunities for professional development (Bektas et al., 2022).

Effective school support is essential for enhancing teacher productivity. Adequate administrative support ensures that teachers' concerns are addressed, and necessary resources are provided. Peer support fosters a collaborative working environment that encourages the sharing of experiences and resources (Chan et al., 2021). A conducive learning environment, equipped with adequate facilities and resources, can significantly reduce non-instructional stressors for teachers, allowing them to focus on teaching. Active parental involvement reinforces teaching initiatives at home, while professional development opportunities help teachers continually improve their skills and adapt to evolving educational demands (Mahoney et al., 2021; Haug & Mork, 2021).

Conversely, a lack of school support can have detrimental effects on teachers' job satisfaction, motivation, and overall productivity (Baroudi et al., 2022). Teachers who do not receive adequate support are more likely to experience stress and burnout, leading to higher turnover rates and instability within the school system. This instability can disrupt student learning and ultimately lower the quality of education (Sahito & Vaisanen, 2020).

In the Philippines, where educational challenges are compounded by diverse geographical and socio-economic conditions, teacher productivity is particularly critical. The effectiveness of Filipino teachers is not only a product of their individual competencies but is also significantly influenced by the level of support they receive within their school system (Baylan, 2018). Supportive school environments can empower teachers to deliver high-quality instruction and maintain a nurturing atmosphere for learning. Administrative support in addressing teacher concerns, strong peer networks fostering collaboration, a stress-reducing learning environment, active parental involvement, and continuous professional development are all crucial components of an effective support system (Abolucion et al., 2020).

Despite the recognized importance of school support in enhancing teacher productivity, there remains a gap in the literature, particularly in the context of the Philippines. While existing studies have explored individual aspects of school support, a comprehensive, multidimensional analysis of how these supports collectively impact teacher productivity is lacking. This study aims to address this gap by examining the various dimensions of school support and their collective influence on teacher productivity in the Philippine setting.

Understanding the impacts of school support on teacher productivity is vital for identifying areas where school systems can improve. The findings from this research will have significant implications for school administrators, policymakers, teachers, and parents, contributing to the overall improvement of education quality and student outcomes in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This research determines the extent of instruction related support in the identified schools in Trinidad, Bohol during the School Year 2022-2023 as Basis for Strategic Plan.

Specifically, this answers the following questions,

1. What relevant information can be derived from the teachers and administrators:
 - 1.1. age and gender,
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment,
 - 1.3. years of service,
 - 1.4. performance,
 - 1.5. relevant leadership training and seminars,
2. As perceived by the respondent groups, what is the extent of instruction related support received by the teachers in terms of the following aspects:
 - 2.1. administrative,
 - 2.2. peer,
 - 2.3. learning environment, and
 - 2.4. professional development
 - 2.5. productivity recognition
 - 2.6. rewards?
3. What is the teacher's performance based on the classroom observation as to:
 - 3.1. teaching/learning activities,
 - 3.2. delivery of content,
 - 3.3. utilization of technology,
4. Is there significant relationship between teachers' performance and the extent of instruction related support received by the teachers?
5. What are the issues and concerns relating to teachers' instruction related support?
6. Based on the findings, what strategic plan can be crafted?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive method of research was employed in this study, which described data and the characteristics of the population under study. This method answered the questions of who, what, where, when, and how. Specifically, the study focused on the present conditions of the respondents concerning the level of teacher support and the perceived issues and concerns by the teachers. The data were described and analyzed based on the information gathered using the research instrument.

This research utilized the INPUT-PROCESS-OUTPUT approach. The INPUT included the demographic profiles of the respondent groups, such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, years of service, and relevant training and seminars attended by teachers and administrators. It also covered the level of teacher support, encompassing constructs such as administrative support, peer support, learning environment, and professional development. Additionally, the research included an analysis of the significant differences between the respondent groups' perceptions of the level of teacher support received and the issues and concerns related to that support.

The PROCESS involved the administration of questionnaires, data consolidation, presentation, analysis, and interpretation using statistical software. The OUTPUT of the study was the proposed strategic plan.

Research Environment

This study was conducted at six elementary schools in Trinidad, Bohol: Banlasan Elementary School, Hinlayagan Ilaya Elementary School, Hinlayagan Ilaud Elementary School (Trinidad Central II Elementary School), Kinan-oan Elementary School, M. Roxas Elementary School, and Maonglinis Elementary School.

Research Participants

The respondents of the study were the teachers and administrators. The respondents were taken for random sampling.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Schools	Administrators	Teachers	Frequency
Banlasan Elementary School	1	30	20
Hinlayagan Ilaya Elementary School	1	30	20
Hinlayagan Ilaud Elementary School	1	30	20
Kinan-oan Elementary School	1	30	20
M. Roxas Elementary School	1	30	20
Maonglinis Elementary School	1	30	20

Total	6	180	120
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Research Instrument

Two different sets of research instruments were utilized in this study to determine the extent of teacher engagement. The Demographic Profile aimed to gather data on the teachers' respective demographic profiles. This checklist collected information such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, years in service, and relevant training and seminars attended.

Administrative Support was adapted from the study by Leithwood, K., Louis, K. S., Anderson, S., & Wahlstrom, K. (2004). These data were analyzed and interpreted to arrive at more conclusive statements and implications. The findings of the study served as a basis for formulating an action plan.

Data Gathering Procedure

A transmittal letter was prepared and addressed to the office of the district superintendent, requesting permission to conduct the study. Once the request was approved, the researcher began distributing questionnaires to the teachers and administrators. The questionnaires were retrieved, and the data were collated. Data and information related to the study were treated with utmost confidence.

Data Analysis

The data gathered using the research instrument were analyzed with the aid of statistical software, employing the following statistical tools:

1. Percentage: This tool was used to show the proportion of a certain variable obtained from the respondents.
2. Weighted Mean: The weighted mean was used to determine the extent of support received by the teachers.
3. T-Test: This test was used to assess significant differences.

Scoring Procedure

A 5-point Likert scale was used to determine the extent of the teacher's support received from the school. The scale was as follows:

Scale	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	The respondents strongly agreed with the statement.
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	The respondents agreed with the statement.
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Agree	The respondents moderately agreed with the statement.
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	The respondents disagreed with the statement.
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	The respondents strongly disagreed with the statement.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the quantitative results related to the following research questions: What are the demographic and professional characteristics of teachers and administrators, including age, gender, highest educational attainment, years of service, relevant leadership training, seminars attended, and performance ratings? It also examines the aspects of instructional support received from administrative channels, peers, and the learning environment. Additionally, it analyzes the professional development opportunities available and the rewards and recognition for productivity. The perceptions of different respondent groups are contrasted to provide a comprehensive view of the state of instructional support in the identified schools in Trinidad, Bohol.

The chapter further evaluates teachers' performance based on DepEd's classroom observation tools, focusing on practical aspects such as teaching and learning activities, content delivery, technology use, language proficiency, and classroom management skills.

The final section investigates the correlations between teachers' performance and the extent of instructional support received. This analysis explores the relationship between support mechanisms and teaching effectiveness, offering insights for guiding future interventions.

Table 2
Age and Gender

Age	Teachers				Administrators			
	Gender		Total		Gender		Total	
	M	F	f	%	M	F	f	%
50 above	0	8	8	4.44	0	0	0	0
46-50	0	10	10	5.56	0	2	1	50
41-45	6	45	51	28.33	0	3	0	50
36-40	7	5	12	6.67	0	0	0	0
31-35	12	23	35	19.44	0	0	0	0
26-30	8	56	64	35.56	0	0	0	0
Total	33	147	180	100	0	5	1	100

Table 2 provides a summary of the age and gender demographics of teachers and administrators. Among the 180 teachers, there were 33 males and 147 females. The largest age group was 26-30, representing 35.56% of teachers, predominantly female. The second largest group was 41-45, comprising 28.33% of teachers, also mostly female. Age groups 31-35 and 46-50 similarly showed more female teachers than males, while the 36-40 group was more balanced. All 8 teachers aged 50 and above were female. The administrator group consisted of 5 females, with 2 in the 46-50 age range and 3 in the 41-45 range. The data highlights a notable gender imbalance, with females significantly outnumbering males in both groups, and indicates that most teachers are under 45, while the administrative group is also predominantly younger.

Table 3
Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Teachers		Administrator	
	f	(%)	f	%
Doctor Degree	24	13.33	4	67
Doctor with units	18	10.00	2	33
Master Degree	23	12.78	0	0
Master with units	77	42.78	0	0
Bachelor Degree	38	21.11	0	0
Total	180	100	6	100

Table 3 presents the highest educational attainment levels of teachers and administrators. Among the 180 teachers, the majority (42.78%) held a Master's Degree with additional units, followed by 21.11% with a Bachelor's Degree. Twelve percent had a Master's Degree without additional units, 13.33% had a Doctorate, and 10% had additional units beyond the Doctorate. Among the 6 administrators, 67% held a Doctoral Degree, and 33% had earned additional units beyond the Doctorate. This indicates that administrators generally have higher educational qualifications compared to teachers, who have a broader range of educational backgrounds.

Table 4
Years of Service

Years of Service	Teachers		Administrator	
	f	%	f	%
26-30	7	3.89	1	16.67
21 -25	9	5.00	1	16.67
16-20	13	7.22	3	50.00
11-15	62	34.44	1	16.67
6-10	38	21.11	0	0
1-5	51	28.33	0	0
Total	180	100	6	100

Table 4 details the years of service among teachers and administrators. For the 180 teachers, the majority (34.44%) had 11-15 years of service, followed by 28.33% with 1-5 years and 21.11% with 6-10 years. Fewer teachers were in the 16-20 years (7.22%), 21-25 years (5.00%), and 26-30 years (3.89%) categories. Among the 6 administrators, 50% had 16-20 years of service, while 16.67% had 21-25 years and 26-30 years each. The remaining 16.67% had 11-15 years of service. This indicates that teachers have a broader distribution of service years, whereas administrators generally have more years of experience. No individuals in either group had more than 30 years of service.

**Table 5
Teachers' Performance**

Performance	Teachers		Administrator	
	f	%	f	%
Outstanding	0	0	0	0
Very Satisfactory	180	100	6	100
Satisfactory	0	0	0	0
Total	180	100	6	100

Table 5 displays the performance evaluations of teachers and administrators. All 180 teachers were rated as 'Very Satisfactory,' representing 100% of the group. Similarly, all 6 administrators also received a 'Very Satisfactory' rating, accounting for 100% of their group. There were no individuals rated as 'Outstanding' or 'Satisfactory' in either group. This indicates a consistent performance evaluation across both teachers and administrators, with all rated 'Very Satisfactory.'

**Table 6
Training and Seminar**

Training and Seminars	Frequency, f
Effective Classroom Management	156
Instructional Technology Integration	120
Teaching Strategies for Diverse Learners	87
Building Emotional Intelligence in the Classroom	167
Student-Centered Learning	123

Table 6 presents the frequency of participation in various training sessions and seminars. The 'Building Emotional Intelligence in the Classroom' seminar had the highest attendance, with 167 participants. This was followed by 'Effective Classroom Management' with 156 participants and 'Student-Centered Learning' with 123 participants. 'Instructional Technology Integration' had 120 participants, while 'Teaching Strategies for Diverse Learners' had the lowest attendance, with 87 participants. This data indicates that seminars on emotional intelligence and classroom management were the most popular, suggesting high interest or need in these areas. Conversely, the lower attendance for 'Teaching Strategies for Diverse Learners' may reflect reduced perceived importance or other barriers to participation.

**Table 7
Administrative Support**

Administrative Support	Administrator		Teachers	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The school administration actively addresses my concerns and problems.	4.33	SA	3.85	A
The school administration provides me with the necessary resources to do my job effectively.	3.67	A	3.20	A
The school administration encourages and facilitates professional development opportunities.	4.17	A	3.80	A

The school administration effectively communicates school policies and changes.	4.00	A	3.70	A
The school administration provides adequate non-instructional time (for planning, grading, etc).	3.67	A	3.60	A
Grand Mean	3.96	A	3.63	A

Table 7 summarizes the perceived level of administrative support from both administrators and teachers. Administrators reported a higher overall level of support with a grand mean of 3.96, categorized as 'Agree.' They strongly agreed that the administration addresses their concerns (mean score of 4.33) and encourages professional development (mean score of 4.17). Effective communication of policies and adequate non-instructional time also received positive ratings, though slightly lower (means of 4.00 and 3.67, respectively).

Teachers reported a slightly lower overall support level with a grand mean of 3.63, also in the 'Agree' category. They felt most supported regarding the administration's response to concerns (mean score of 3.85). Professional development opportunities and communication of policies were rated positively as well (means of 3.80 and 3.70). However, teachers rated the provision of necessary resources (mean score of 3.20) and non-instructional time (mean score of 3.60) lower compared to administrators.

This data indicates that while both groups generally feel supported, there are areas—particularly regarding resources and non-instructional time for teachers—that could benefit from improvement.

Table 8
Peer Support

Peer Support	Administrator		Teachers	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
My colleagues are willing to share teaching materials and experiences.	4.00	A	3.70	A
I feel supported by my fellow teachers in handling classroom challenges.	4.17	A	3.60	A
There is a strong sense of community among the staff at my school.	3.67	A	3.40	A
There are opportunities for collaboration and team teaching in my school.	4.17	A	3.50	A
Peer mentoring programs are available and effective in my school.	4.00	A	3.60	A
Grand Mean	4.00	A	3.56	A

Table 8 evaluates peer support perceptions among administrators and teachers. Administrators reported high peer support with a grand mean of 4.00, categorized as 'Agree'. They particularly valued colleagues' willingness to share materials (mean score of 4.00) and support in handling classroom challenges (mean score of 4.17). Opportunities for collaboration and the effectiveness of peer mentoring programs also received high ratings (means of 4.17 and 4.00, respectively). The sense of community among staff scored slightly lower at 3.67 but still within the 'Agree' category.

Teachers also perceived positive peer support with a grand mean of 3.56. They felt supported by colleagues in sharing materials (mean score of 3.70) and in handling classroom challenges (mean score of 3.60). However, opportunities for collaboration (mean score of 3.50) and the sense of community (mean score of 3.40) received slightly lower ratings. Peer mentoring programs were rated at 3.60. Overall, both administrators and teachers perceive good peer support, but improvements could be made in enhancing the sense of community and increasing collaborative opportunities.

Table 9
Learning Environment

Learning Environment	Administrator		Teachers	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The physical environment of the school (e.g., classrooms, facilities) supports effective teaching.	4.00	A	3.50	A
There is adequate technology available for instruction.	4.00	A	3.90	A
Classroom size allows for effective teaching and learning.	4.00	A	3.55	A
The school culture is conducive to teaching and learning.	4.17	A	3.20	MA
The school provides effective tools for remote/distance learning	4.17	A	3.60	A
Grand Mean	4.07	A	3.55	A

Table 9 assesses perceptions of the learning environment. Administrators rated their learning environment positively with a grand mean of 4.07, falling in the 'Agree' category. They agreed that the physical environment (mean score of 4.00), technology availability (mean score of 4.00), and classroom size (mean score of 4.00) support effective teaching. The school culture and remote learning tools were rated slightly higher at 4.17.

Teachers reported a lower grand mean score of 3.55, also within the 'Agree' category. They agreed that technology (mean score of 3.90) and the physical environment (mean score of 3.50) support teaching but rated the school culture (mean score of 3.20) as only 'Moderate Agreement'. Classroom size and tools for remote learning were rated at 3.55 and 3.60, respectively. Both groups generally find the learning environment supportive, though there is room for improvement in school culture and possibly physical resources and classroom sizes.

Table 10
Professional Development

Professional Development	Administrator		Teachers	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The school provides ongoing professional development opportunities.	4.00	A	3.45	A
Professional development activities are relevant to my teaching context.	4.17	A	3.40	A
There are opportunities to learn from and share best practices with other teachers.	4.00	A	3.65	A
The school supports my growth as a professional educator.	4.17	A	3.60	A

Grand Mean	4.09	A	3.52	A
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Table 10 details perceptions of professional development. Administrators expressed high satisfaction with a grand mean score of 4.09, indicating 'Agree'. They felt that development activities are relevant (mean score of 4.17) and that the school supports their growth (mean score of 4.17). They also agreed that there are ongoing opportunities (mean score of 4.00) and chances to share best practices (mean score of 4.00).

Teachers also had positive views, though with a lower grand mean score of 3.52. They particularly appreciated opportunities to share best practices (mean score of 3.65) and felt supported in their professional growth (mean score of 3.60). The relevance of development activities (mean score of 3.40) and ongoing opportunities (mean score of 3.45) received slightly lower ratings. Both administrators and teachers view professional development positively, but there is potential for improvement in the relevance and continuity of these opportunities.

Table 11
Productivity Recognition

Productivity Recognition	Administrator		Teachers	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
My institution frequently recognizes my productivity in instruction-related tasks.	4.17	A	3.20	MA
There is a system in place that consistently recognizes high productivity among teachers.	4.17	A	3.20	MA
I feel valued and appreciated for my productivity in my role as a teacher.	3.33	MA	3.25	A
My institution's recognition of my productivity motivates me to maintain or improve my performance.	3.83	A	3.45	A
There is a clear and transparent process to evaluate and recognize productivity in my institution.	4.17	A	3.20	MA
Grand Mean	3.93	A	3.26	MA

Table 11 outlines the perceptions of administrators and teachers regarding productivity recognition within their institution. Administrators reported a high level of satisfaction with productivity recognition, reflected in a grand mean score of 3.93, categorized as 'Agree'. They felt that their productivity in instruction-related tasks was frequently recognized (mean score of 4.17), that there is a system in place for recognizing high productivity (mean score of 4.17), and that there is a clear and transparent evaluation process (mean score of 4.17). They also felt that recognition motivates them to improve performance (mean score of 3.83). However, administrators felt less strongly about being valued and appreciated for their productivity (mean score of 3.33), which falls into the 'Moderate Agreement' category.

Teachers perceived productivity recognition at a slightly lower level, with a grand mean score of 3.26, categorized as 'Moderate Agreement'. They felt most positively about the motivation provided by recognition (mean score of 3.45) and that they feel valued for

their productivity (mean score of 3.25). However, the frequency of recognition, the system for high productivity, and the transparency of the evaluation process all received lower scores (mean scores of 3.20), indicating 'Moderate Agreement'. This suggests a need for improvement in how teachers feel recognized and appreciated for their contributions, as well as in enhancing the clarity and frequency of productivity recognition.

Table 12
Rewards

Rewards	Administrator		Teachers	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
My institution provides adequate rewards for instruction-related accomplishments.	4.17	A	3.60	A
Tangible rewards (e.g., bonuses, promotions) are regularly provided to teachers for their instruction-related achievements.	4.00	A	3.45	A
The reward system for instruction-related achievements in my institution is fair and just.	4.17	A	3.40	A
Rewards for instruction-related work significantly enhance my job satisfaction.	4.00	A	3.65	A
The rewards I receive are proportionate to the effort I invest in instruction-related tasks.	3.67	A	3.60	A
Grand Mean	4.00	A	3.54	A

Table 12 evaluates the perceptions of administrators and teachers regarding rewards for instruction-related accomplishments. Administrators expressed high satisfaction with the rewards provided, with a grand mean score of 4.00, falling in the 'Agree' category. They agreed that their institution provides adequate rewards (mean score of 4.17), that the reward system is fair and just (mean score of 4.17), and that tangible rewards are regularly provided (mean score of 4.00). They also felt that rewards significantly enhance job satisfaction (mean score of 4.00) and that the rewards are proportional to their efforts (mean score of 3.67).

Teachers also had a positive view of the rewards system, with a grand mean score of 3.54, still within the 'Agree' category. They agreed that the institution provides adequate rewards (mean score of 3.60) and that the rewards are proportional to their efforts (mean score of 3.60). They also felt that rewards significantly enhance job satisfaction (mean score of 3.65). However, they rated the regular provision of tangible rewards and the fairness of the reward system slightly lower (mean scores of 3.45 and 3.40, respectively), though these still fall within the 'Agree' category. Overall, both administrators and teachers find the rewards for instruction-related accomplishments satisfactory, but there is room for improvement, especially in enhancing the fairness and regularity of tangible rewards as perceived by teachers.

Table 13
Teaching/Learning Activities

Indicators	Rating	Performance
The teacher effectively uses a variety of teaching strategies appropriate to the lesson.	90	VS
The teacher promotes active learning and engages all students in learning activities.	91	VS
The teacher differentiates instruction to accommodate diverse learners.	88	VS
The teacher facilitates group work and collaborative learning effectively.	90	VS
The teacher consistently integrates formative assessment strategies during the lesson.	89	VS
Grand Mean	89.6	VS

Table 13 evaluates a teacher's performance in Teaching/Learning Activities, with an overall "Very Satisfactory" rating and a grand mean of 89.6. The teacher excelled in promoting active learning and engaging students, achieving a high rating of 91. Other notable areas include the effective use of diverse teaching strategies and facilitating group work, each rated at 90. The teacher was also rated "Very Satisfactory" in differentiating instruction (88) and integrating formative assessments (89), demonstrating strong performance across all indicators.

Table 14
Delivery of Content

Indicators	Rating	Performance
The teacher presents content accurately and clearly.	89	VS
The teacher connects the content to students' prior knowledge and experiences.	90	VS
The teacher provides clear and concise instructions and explanations.	90	VS
The teacher uses relevant and relatable examples to explain concepts.	89	VS
The teacher encourages students to ask questions and express their thoughts about the content.	89	VS
The teacher presents content accurately and clearly.	89	VS
Grand Mean	89	VS

Table 14 assesses the Delivery of Content, where the teacher received a grand mean rating of 89, indicating "Very Satisfactory" performance. The teacher's highest ratings were for connecting content to students' prior knowledge and providing clear instructions, both scoring 90. Other areas such as presenting content accurately, using relevant examples, and encouraging student questions all received a rating of 89, reflecting the teacher's effective communication and engagement strategies.

**Table 15
Utilization of Technology**

Indicators	Rating	Performance
The teacher integrates technology into lessons effectively when applicable.	90	VS
The teacher demonstrates confidence and proficiency in using technology.	90	VS
The teacher uses technology to promote interactive and engaging learning.	89	VS
The teacher uses technology to differentiate and personalize instruction.	89	VS
The teacher uses technology to provide feedback and assess student learning.	90	VS
Grand Mean	89.6	VS

Table 15 evaluates the Utilization of Technology, with a grand mean rating of 89.6, also marking "Very Satisfactory" performance. The teacher scored 90 in integrating technology into lessons and demonstrating proficiency, while technology's use in promoting interactive learning and differentiation received ratings of 89. These scores suggest a strong capability in leveraging technology to enhance teaching, although the teacher's integration of technology may be associated with slightly lower scores in some support areas.

**Table 16
Significant Relationship Between Teaching/Learning Activities and Instruction Related Support**

	<i>Teaching/Learning Activities</i>	<i>Administrative</i>	<i>Peer</i>	<i>learning environment</i>	<i>professional development</i>	<i>productivity recognition</i>
Teaching/Learning Activities	1					
Administrative	-0.62685	1				
Peer	0.615385	-0.16095	1			
learning environment	0.263117	-0.72438	0.263117	1		
professional development	-0.79112	0.5986	-0.85492	-0.64499	1	
productivity recognition	0.040456	0.231663	-0.46524	-0.80721	0.565946	1
rewards	0.262962	0.302944	0.46524	-0.64577	-0.06263	0.43617

Table 16 examines the relationship between Teaching/Learning Activities and various forms of instruction-related support. The data reveals a negative correlation between teaching/learning activities and administrative support (-0.62685), but a positive correlation with peer support (0.615385). The teacher's performance in teaching activities is less strongly related to professional development and productivity recognition, highlighting areas where support may impact effectiveness differently.

Table 17
Significant Relationship Between Delivery of Content and Instruction Related Support

	<i>Delivery of Content</i>	<i>Administrative</i>	<i>Peer</i>	<i>learning environment</i>	<i>professional development</i>	<i>productivity recognition</i>
Delivery of Content	1					
Administrative	-0.45847	1				
Peer	-0.48038	-0.16095	1			
learning environment	0.63901	-0.72438	0.263117	1		
professional development	0.008854	0.5986	-0.85492	-0.64499	1	
productivity recognition	-0.29475	0.231663	-0.46524	-0.80721	0.565946	1
rewards	-0.96847	0.302944	0.46524	-0.64577	-0.06263	0.43617

Table 17 explores the relationship between Delivery of Content and instruction-related support. It shows a positive correlation with the learning environment (0.63901) but negative correlations with administrative support (-0.45847) and peer support (-0.48038). These findings suggest that while effective content delivery is associated with a positive learning environment, it may come at the expense of other support areas.

Table 18
Significant Relationship Between Utilization of Technology and Instruction Related Support

	<i>utilization of technology</i>	<i>Administrative</i>	<i>Peer</i>	<i>learning environment</i>	<i>professional development</i>	<i>productivity recognition</i>
utilization of technology	1					
Administrative	-0.42321	1				
Peer	0.880705	-0.16095	1			
learning environment	0.63901	-0.72438	0.263117	1		
professional development	-0.89426	0.5986	-0.85492	-0.64499	1	
productivity recognition	-0.75794	0.231663	-0.46524	-0.80721	0.565946	1
rewards	0.126323	0.302944	0.46524	-0.64577	-0.06263	0.43617

Table 18 details the relationships between Utilization of Technology and instruction-related support. It highlights a strong positive correlation with peer support (0.880705) and a moderate correlation with the learning environment (0.63901). However, it also shows negative correlations with administrative support (-0.42321), professional development (-0.89426), and productivity recognition (-0.75794), indicating potential trade-offs in balancing technology use with other support factors.

Table 19
Perceived Issues and Concerns

Indicator	Rank
Assessment and accountability pressures	1
Insufficient peer support	2
Limited autonomy in decision-making	3
Inadequate support for technology integration	4
Challenging learning environment	5
Lack of recognition and rewards	6
Limited access to learning resources:	7

Table 19 identifies key issues and concerns related to instruction support, ranked by importance. The top concern is "Assessment and accountability pressures," reflecting significant stress related to high-stakes testing. "Insufficient peer support" follows, emphasizing the need for better collaboration among teachers. Other concerns include "Limited autonomy in decision-making," "Inadequate support for technology integration," "Challenging learning environment," "Lack of recognition and rewards," and "Limited access to learning resources," all highlighting various areas where improvements could enhance instructional effectiveness and teacher satisfaction.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The highlights of the findings of this study are the following:

1. The research data reveals several key findings across various dimensions of the educational environment. Firstly, there is a significant gender imbalance among teachers, with females overwhelmingly outnumbering males, particularly in the younger age groups, while all administrators are female and mostly aged between 41-50 years. Educational attainment among teachers varies, with a majority holding a Master's Degree with additional units, whereas most administrators possess a Doctoral Degree. In terms of service years, teachers are broadly distributed across different experience levels, with the majority having 11-15 years of service, while administrators generally have more experience, with most having 16-20 years of service.

2. Performance evaluations indicate a uniform 'Very Satisfactory' rating for all teachers and administrators, showing consistent performance across both groups. Participation in training and seminars is highest in areas like emotional intelligence and classroom management, suggesting these are areas of particular focus or need. The level of administrative and peer support is perceived positively by both teachers and administrators, though administrators report slightly higher satisfaction, especially in addressing concerns and facilitating professional development.

3. Regarding the learning environment, both groups agree that the physical environment, technology, and classroom size are supportive, though teachers express moderate agreement with the school's culture. Professional development opportunities

are generally seen as beneficial, with administrators expressing higher satisfaction, particularly in relevance and support for growth. Finally, recognition of productivity is viewed more positively by administrators, while teachers feel less recognized, indicating a potential area for improvement in recognizing and motivating teaching staff. Overall, while the data indicates a generally supportive and satisfactory educational environment, it also highlights areas such as gender balance, resource provision, and productivity recognition that could benefit from targeted improvements.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study provides a comprehensive overview of the educational environment, highlighting several critical insights. The gender imbalance among teachers, particularly in younger age groups, alongside the predominance of female administrators, underscores the need for more gender diversity in educational leadership and teaching roles. The varying levels of educational attainment and years of service between teachers and administrators reflect a diverse workforce, but also suggest opportunities for further professional development, particularly among teachers seeking higher qualifications.

The uniform 'Very Satisfactory' performance ratings suggest a consistently high standard of work among both teachers and administrators, although the disparity in recognition of productivity between these groups indicates a need for more equitable acknowledgment of efforts across the board. The positive perception of administrative and peer support, as well as the physical and technological learning environment, demonstrates a solid foundation for educational success. However, the moderate satisfaction with school culture among teachers and their lower levels of recognition point to areas where institutional support could be enhanced.

Overall, the findings suggest that while the educational environment is largely effective and supportive, targeted improvements in gender diversity, professional recognition, and cultural inclusivity could further enhance the experience and effectiveness of both teachers and administrators. Addressing these areas would not only contribute to the personal and professional growth of educators but also support the continued development of a positive and productive learning environment for students.

Recommendations

The main goal of this study is to gain knowledge on the level of the extent of instruction related support in the identified schools in Trinidad, Bohol during the School Year 2022-2023 as Basis for Strategic Plan. It is recommended that the proposed Strategic Plan crafted shall be considered for implementation.

OUTPUT OF THE STUDY

This section contains Strategic Activities in based on the findings of the study entitled “**ENHANCING TEACHER PRODUCTIVITY THROUGH SCHOOL SUPPORTS**”. It serves as a proposal to the department of Education and local government units

Rationale

The proposal to the Department of Education and local government units for implementing strategic activities based on the findings of the study titled "Enhancing Teacher Productivity through School Supports" is grounded in the need to improve teacher productivity and create a supportive educational environment. The study's findings have shed light on crucial factors influencing teacher effectiveness, including administrative support, peer support, learning environment, professional development, recognition and rewards, and technology integration. Implementing strategic activities, we aim to address the identified issues, capitalize on the positive aspects, and foster a culture of continuous improvement within the educational system.

Firstly, addressing the identified issues, such as assessment pressures, limited peer support, and inadequate technology integration, is essential for improving teacher productivity. These strategic activities will provide targeted solutions, such as developing support systems to alleviate assessment pressures, implementing peer mentoring programs to enhance collaboration, and investing in technology resources and training to support effective integration.

Secondly, capitalizing on the positive aspects identified in the study, such as favorable ratings for administrative support, peer support, and the learning environment, is crucial for sustaining and enhancing teacher productivity. The proposed activities will focus on strengthening these areas further, ensuring that administrative support systems are responsive, fostering a strong sense of community and collaboration among teachers, and creating an optimal learning environment with adequate resources and technology infrastructure.

Thirdly, supporting teachers' professional development is vital for their continuous growth and increased productivity. The proposed activities include providing ongoing professional development opportunities that are relevant to teachers' needs, facilitating the sharing of best practices among teachers, and creating a supportive culture that values and supports teachers' growth as professionals. Additionally, recognizing and rewarding teachers' productivity is crucial for their motivation and job satisfaction. The proposed activities will establish transparent systems for evaluating and recognizing productivity, ensure fairness in the reward system, and develop mechanisms for regularly acknowledging teachers' accomplishments.

Ultimately, the rationale behind these strategic activities is to foster a supportive and empowering environment for teachers, as they play a critical role in delivering quality education to students. By addressing the identified issues, capitalizing on positive aspects, and providing necessary support and resources, we can enhance teacher

productivity and create a sustainable educational system that benefits both educators and learners. The collaboration between the Department of Education, local government units, teachers, and other stakeholders is essential for the successful implementation of these activities and the continuous improvement of the educational system.

Objectives

- Enhance Administrative Support
- Foster Peer Support and Collaboration
- Optimize the Learning Environment
- Enhance Professional Development Opportunities
- Improve Recognition and Rewards

Scheme of Implementation

The output of this study will be addressed to the department of education and identified schools for deliberation and possible implementation.

STRATEGIC PLAN

Objective 1: Enhance Administrative Support

Establish regular communication channels

Implement a system for open and transparent communication between teachers and administrators, such as regular staff meetings, suggestion boxes, and online platforms, to address concerns and provide timely feedback.

Develop a resource allocation plan

Ensure that administrators allocate necessary resources, such as instructional materials, technology equipment, and classroom supplies, in a fair and equitable manner to support teachers' job effectiveness.

Provide mentoring and coaching

Assign experienced administrators or senior teachers as mentors to provide guidance and support to new teachers, helping them navigate challenges and maximize their effectiveness in the classroom.

Conduct professional development for administrators

Offer training programs and workshops specifically designed for administrators to enhance their leadership and management skills, enabling them to better support and understand the needs of teachers.

Establish a teacher feedback system

Implement a structured feedback mechanism where teachers can provide input and suggestions to administrators regarding school policies, procedures, and support systems, ensuring their voices are heard and taken into consideration.

Objective 2: Foster Peer Support and Collaboration

Encourage collaborative planning and sharing of resources

Facilitate regular meetings and workshops that promote collaborative lesson planning, resource sharing, and the exchange of teaching strategies among teachers to enhance peer support.

Implement a buddy system

Pair new or less experienced teachers with experienced mentors who can provide guidance, advice, and support, fostering a strong sense of camaraderie and collaboration within the teaching community.

Establish professional learning communities

Create dedicated groups or communities within the school where teachers with common interests or specialties can come together to share experiences, discuss challenges, and collaborate on projects.

Organize peer observation and feedback sessions

Set up a structured system for teachers to observe each other's classes and provide constructive feedback, encouraging professional growth and the exchange of best practices.

Encourage joint professional development opportunities

Arrange workshops, seminars, or conferences where teachers can attend together, facilitating networking, collaboration, and shared learning experiences.

Objective 3: Optimize the Learning Environment

Invest in technology infrastructure: Ensure that the school has a robust and reliable technology infrastructure, including high-speed internet, up-to-date hardware and software, and interactive learning tools, to support effective instruction and student engagement.

Provide professional development on technology integration

Offer training and workshops for teachers to enhance their skills in utilizing technology effectively for instruction, including online platforms, multimedia resources, and digital assessment tools.

Create flexible learning spaces

Design classrooms and other learning areas that can be easily reconfigured to accommodate different instructional strategies and foster student-centered learning, allowing for collaboration and active participation.

Improve access to learning resources

Develop a comprehensive system for teachers to access a wide range of learning resources, including libraries, digital databases, and online platforms, ensuring they have the necessary materials to support their teaching.

Foster a positive and inclusive school culture

Promote a welcoming and inclusive environment where diversity is celebrated, bullying is not tolerated, and students feel safe and supported, creating a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning.

Objective 4: Enhance Professional Development Opportunities

Conduct needs assessment surveys

Regularly assess the professional development needs and preferences of teachers to design targeted and relevant training programs that address their specific requirements.

Offer a variety of professional development formats

Provide a mix of in-person workshops, online courses, webinars, conferences, and collaborative learning opportunities to accommodate different learning styles and preferences.

Establish partnerships with educational institutions and experts

Collaborate with universities, education experts, and professional organizations to bring in external expertise, offer specialized training programs, and tap into a broader network of resources.

Encourage action research and reflective practice

Promote a culture of continuous learning by encouraging teachers to engage in action research projects and reflective practice, allowing them to evaluate and improve their instructional strategies.

Support teacher-led professional development

Provide opportunities for teachers to lead and facilitate professional development sessions, allowing them to share their expertise, showcase innovative practices, and contribute to the professional growth of their colleagues.

Objective 5: Improve Recognition and Rewards

Establish a recognition program

Create a formal system for acknowledging and celebrating teachers' achievements and contributions, such as "Teacher of the Month" awards, certificates of recognition, or public appreciation events.

Implement a performance-based evaluation process

Develop a transparent and fair performance evaluation system that recognizes and rewards teachers based on their instructional effectiveness, student outcomes, and professional growth.

Provide professional growth incentives

Offer financial incentives, such as salary increments or bonuses, to teachers who actively pursue professional development opportunities, earn additional qualifications, or demonstrate exceptional teaching practices.

Showcase teachers' success stories

Share success stories and exemplary practices of teachers through newsletters, school websites, or social media platforms, highlighting their achievements and inspiring others.

Involve teachers in decision-making processes

Ensure that teachers have a voice in decision-making processes that affect their work and professional growth, allowing them to contribute ideas and perspectives on recognition and reward systems.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Any ethical concerns that could have risen throughout the study were resolved by securing necessary permits. Also, the researcher personally handed the research tools to the schools, with the assistance of the administrators, which included the informed consent form and questionnaires. Before data collection began, all research terms and conditions were fully disclosed to maintain transparency. Despite receiving clearance from the school principals and administrators, the researcher obtained informed consent from participants by individually requesting them to participate and providing thorough information about the study, including potential risks and benefits, as well as privacy safeguards. Each participant was asked to review and sign the informed consent form, indicating their comprehension and willingness to be involved in the study. It was optional to provide the participants' names, which were coded to preserve their identity. To safeguard data, further confidentiality measures were put in place, such as limiting access to physical and electronic resources. The study closely followed data privacy and research ethics guidelines, and participants were made aware of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any moment without facing consequences.

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